

THE SPECIFIC IMPORTANCE OF MOTOR METHODS OF SPECIAL TRAINING IN SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNING

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Annotation. This article covers the activities of short-distance runners in the training process and the state of duration of training. In the process of training, an increase in physical loads and the process of influence of athletes is expressed, depending on the state of the workout. At the same time, the schedule of the weekly plan in the organization of the study was expressed as a basis.

Keywords: short distance, sports training, physical loads, strength training, speed strength, special strength, special training, training process, physical condition.

Introduction

It is known that at present in our Republic there is a huge amount of work on improving the living well-being of the population, improving health, improving physical education and sports among the population, educating the younger generation of our future as mature and physically competent in all respects.

The formation of Uzbekistan as an independent state and its bold progress towards independence necessitates further improvement of socio-economic, political, cultural and educational spheres. Along the way, deep reforms are being carried out in the fields of Health, Science, Culture, Technology, Economics, Education, Physical Education and sports, as well as head.

As you know, the main goal is to establish and manage these processes based on the requirements of the present day. The upbringing of a harmonious person in the boskich of the current period of development of society is one of the most basic, non-procrastinating important tasks.

Therefore, the work carried out in the field of sports in our republic has a great influence on the high performance of young people in prestigious competitions. At this point, very large changes are also being made in the sports athletics type.

It is desirable that the trainees of the short-distance runner training group solve the following tasks during the annual preparatory cycle.

It consists in the comprehensive harmonic development of the handlers and an increase in their special physical training.

The action of increasing UJT consists in improving the activity of the base apparatus and the internal organism.

The next stage of preparation is special preparation, this stage solves specific tasks. Firstly, it is at this stage that an athlete is put to increase his special physical ability to work, and secondly, motor methods are used that are aimed at increasing the physical qualities of quick strength and fast endurance. Of the many leading scientists, N.G.Nikitushkin, N.N.Chesnakov, V.G.Bauer, V.B.Zelichenok, K.T.In their research, shakirzhonovas indicated in their work that

they devote 15-20 weeks to the period of special training. But the downloads in this special training period and the motor methods used in it have not shown to what extent the sports result will affect growth. The main method of sports training. Exercises, that is, the method of repeated execution of movements, are considered.

Depending on the training tasks and the capabilities of track and field athletes, the method varies in different forms (variable, repeated, rotating, intermittent, even, control, competition, etc.).k)

Short distance runners the main means of training is running at maximum speed. The means of training short-distance runners are divided into two groups, depending on their similarity to the type of competition activity: special and non-specific. Special tools are close to the competition activities of short-distance runners according to their kinematic, denamic and energetic characteristics. Non-specific exercises are used as a means of general physical fitness, and their training effect is not great. However, the greater use of training tools that increase overall physical fitness during adolescence allows for a good foundation and painless transitions to adult discharge to adolescents. For the development of speed capabilities, running on a slope (slope angle 240) is used in mitigated conditions. In this case, the best effect can be achieved if running on a slope is alternated with running along the horizon and running on a hill (mountain). Running in relaxed conditions is simple and with running in harsh conditions 1:1:2, 1:2:1, 2:1:1 alternation in proportions should be applied. Performing exercises in difficult conditions should be alternated in proportions 2:1 or 1:1 with simple execution. At the start acceleration, the muscles that break through the thigh and calf perform the main stresses. Various special training techniques are used to develop strength characteristics of different muscle groups. General strength training, speed strength training are considered such techniques. During the base period of the athlete, the mechanical effect of the track with the surface should be formed in such a way that it is necessary that the main force vector is directed not upwards, but more forward. For this, the method of developing a special force is used when running with resistance. It is carried out using resistance in running, strength training allows you to develop strength and speed compositions in direct starting conditions. Such training gives a greater effect than traditional strength exercises performed with resistance. When developing a strategy for training athletes, it should be taken into account that speed is indicators in which strength and intensity are closely related. They are supplied through the holistic system of the organism. In severe intense work, the structure of muscle fibers can change, which can lead to a loss of balance. It is necessary that the coaches take note of the changes and approach the strength training of short-distance runners in a strictly individual way. Foreign healers believe that strength training should serve to improve more nerve muscle coordination than the growth of muscle groups. In this regard, long-term strong work performed using traditional exercises is a mistake, so it is advisable to perform strength exercises at maximum speed, overcoming the weight of the body. Therefore, to increase the pace and length of the running steps, it is recommended to perform strength exercises with a characteristic structure for short-distance runner movements. To do this, in training, as well as from familiar running and jumping exercises, many jumps on both one and the other leg, jumping from not too high hills and jogging forward, multi-squats for speed at a distance of 80m with acceleration, running along the marks and in different conditions, running on the sidewalk in different distance sections, running with a change

In a conversation with trainers who train short-distance runners, many coaches know the size of their approximate planning and loading of annual training, but the intensity of the application and execution of the tools, how much they will be for the intermediate duration, is also not known by some coaches. And this is due to the fact that the ratio of universal training and special physical training loads in the distribution of annual training loads will definitely not remain without affecting the growth of sports results. According to many scientists, the main problems are training and tool, the sequence of methods volume of training loads have suggested the following areas of their relationship with intensity:

- reduction of the load of special preparation from the loads during the preparation period;
- weekly training to increase the intensity and volume of special downloads;
- the training focused on the management methodology between rest in large and small intensity zones.

Training of the annual preparatory period was able to compete, scientifically based work on the activities of the competition and the interval of rest, on the directions of the aerobic anaerobic interval, is rare.

One of the techniques for improving speed qualities is a special traction system, which allows you to perform both forward and backward runs, changing direction from time to time using tyaga. This exercise is recommended for qualified short-distance runners who have been preparing for a long time in short-distance running.

We bring the structure of weekly loadouts, which are applicable for short-distance runners 14-16 years old, belonging to the experimental group.

These physical loads have a great influence on the high level of development of the training process and physical condition for athletes running short distances. We will see the tables of this plan below. When it comes to corruption in education, a thousand unfortunately continue to increase as much as it is fought against it.

Monday: the development of physical qualities of operational-strength to increase UJT.

- 1.Light running 30 m.
- 2.Special running exercise 2x50m
- 3.Acceleration running 6x50m.
- 4.Running jumping from foot to foot 6x50 m.
- 5.Work with weighted trainers.
- 6.Closing run.

Tuesday: development of General and special endurance.

- 1.Light running 1200 m.
- 2.ORM 15 min.
- 3.Gymnastics and flexionnivojlan-climbing exercises.
- 4.Accelerated runs 4x50 m.
- 5.Repeated runs 2x100 m, 2x150 m, 2x200 m Performance intensity 85-95%.
- 6.Sports game 15 min.
7. Closing run.

Wednesday: Power prompt-develop the quality of power.

1. Free exercise 30 min.
2. Work with a stuffing ball.
3. Work with weighted bodies.
- 4.Jumping exercises 15 min.

5. Closing run 1200 m.

Thursday: relax swimming 1 hour.

Friday: increase in all-round training, develop the quality of fast strength.

1. Free exercise 30 min.

2. To doing exercises with an improvised ball is 15 min.

3. Core thrust (4 kg and correctly assessing physical condition) 15 min.

4. Jumping exercises 10 min.

5. Acceleration running 2x60 m.

6. Game 15 min. (sports and action games)

7. Closing run 800 m.

Saturday: the harmonic development of each setting and the education of special endurance.

1. Grass 6 km (1km 5,20,0).

2. ORM 10 min.

3. Acceleration running 2x100 m.

4. Game 20 min. (sports and action games)

5. The closing run is 1200 km.

Sunday: relaxation, bath, sauna, cultural leisure.

The weekly schedule of the exercise shown above serves as the main tool for short-distance running athletes in the competition of movement opportunities.

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